

The Effect of A-DNA and B-DNA Conformation on the Interplay between Local Excitations and Charge-Transfer States in the Ultrafast Decay of Guanine-Cytosine Stacked Dimers: A Quantum Dynamical Investigation

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Abstract

We here simulate in the gas phase the population dynamics of guanine/cytosine (GC) and cytosine/guanine (CG) stacked dimer in B-DNA and A-DNA arrangement, following excitation in the lowest energy band, and considering the four lowest energy $\pi\pi^*$ bright excited states, the three lowest energy $n\pi^*$ states, and the G \rightarrow C Charge Transfer (CT) state. We resort to a generalized Linear Vibronic Coupling model (LVC) parameterized with time-dependent density functional theory computations (TD-DFT), exploiting a fragment based diabaticization and we run nonadiabatic quantum dynamical simulations with the multilayer-version of the Multiconfigurational Time Dependent Hartree (ML-MCTDH) approach. G \rightarrow C CT results a major decay process for GC in B-DNA, but less in A-DNA arrangement, where also the population transfer to the lowest energy excited state localized on C is an important inter-monomer process. In CG arrangements mostly intra-monomeric decays take place. We simulate the dynamics of several other GC structures, whose arrangement is intermediate between B-DNA and A-DNA, obtaining further insights on the effect that the sequence and, especially, the stacking geometry have on the population transfer to the G \rightarrow C CT.

1 Introduction

In the last decades, the study of the photoactivated dynamics of nucleic acids (NAs) has been a very lively research field for chemical research, because of the potential pathological relevance of the photochemical reactions triggered in DNA by the absorption of UV light.^{1,2} The application of always more sensitive and better time resolved experimental techniques, interpreted with the help of quantum mechanical calculations of increasing accuracy, has enabled significant advances in our understanding of the excited processes either responsible of damaging the genetic code or, alternatively, allowing to dissipate in heat the energy deposited on DNA by UV irradiation.²⁻⁸ Experiments and calculations show that a complex interplay between excited states of different nature is operative,²⁻⁹ the population of excited states with significant charge transfer (CT) character between two stacked bases¹⁰ appearing a key event.^{3,9,11,12} Indeed experiments on several oligonucleotide single strands, including dinucleotides, indicate that a significant part of the excited state population decays to charge transfer exciplexes,^{3,5,13-18} recovering the ground state by charge recombination. A quite similar picture is obtained in duplexes and quadruplexes, where the intrastrand CT processes¹⁹⁻²¹ can lead to interstrand proton transfer, resulting in a proton coupled electron transfer processes.^{19,22-27} The experimental indications are fully confirmed by many computational studies, either static or dynamical.^{11,28-34}

Most of the available results, both experimental and computational, concern DNA sequences, which have been investigated more thoroughly due to the medical relevance of photodamaging the genetic code. On the other hand, a few experimental results are available also on RNA sequences.^{13,35-37} Kohler and coll. studied several diribonucleoside monophosphates, including ApA, (A)₄ and polyA by the femtosecond transient-absorption technique.¹³ A long-living excited state is present in all these species, and several experimental evidences indicate that it can be assigned to an intra-strand CT state, involving two stacked bases, whose yield depends on the fraction of stacked bases.¹³ Interestingly, the yield of the long-living excited states in polyA is significantly smaller than in poly(dA), and this difference

has been ascribed to the different stacking geometry of these two polymers.³⁶ A recent study of Chan et al.³⁷ show, indeed, that the photoactivated dynamics of homopolymeric adenine·uracil RNA duplex, which adopts a A-DNA structure, is quite different with respect to that of the corresponding adenine·thymine RNA duplex, in B-DNA arrangement. As a matter of fact, A-DNA and B-DNA, though being both right-handed helices, are quite different. In the former structure there is a slightly larger number of bases for turn, resulting in a shorter average rise of the base pairs along the helix axis ($\sim 2.3 \text{ \AA}$ vs. $\sim 3.3 \text{ \AA}$), but on the same time, a larger inclination of the base pairs with respect to the axis. On the balance, A-DNA helix is shorter and wider than B-DNA one.

It is thus apparent that the formation of intra-strand CT states is strongly modulated by the stacking geometry of the involved bases. This paper aims to get some insights on this issue, and therefore we study the interplay between bright and CT states in two dinucleotide sequences CG and GC, with a stacking geometry typical of B-DNA or A-DNA duplexes. GC and CG arrangements are not equivalent, and they can have a different photophysics.^{29,31}

To reach this goal we build up generalized Linear Vibronic Coupling models (LVC) describing the coupling of local bright and dark excitations and inter-base CT states in different stacked guanine-cytosine (GC) dimers in B-DNA and A-DNA arrangements. We will consider both 5GC3 (hereafter GC) or 5CG3 (CG) sequences depending on whether G is at the 5' end and C at the 3' end or viceversa. Moreover, we simulate in the Supporting Information (SI) the dynamics for several other GC arrangements intermediate between A-DNA and B-DNA. These LVC models are parameterized with time-dependent density functional theory computations (TD-DFT), exploiting a fragment based diabaticization that adopts a maximum-overlap criterion.^{38,39} The time-evolution of the population of the different diabatic states is computed by running nonadiabatic quantum dynamical simulations with the multilayer-version of the Multiconfigurational Time Dependent Hartree (ML-MCTDH) approach.⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴ This approach has been already profitably adopted to simulate the photoactivated dynamics in oligonucleotides,^{29,31,39,45,46} as well as in other multichromophore systems.^{47,48}

We shall show that for GC sequence the population transfer to the G→C CT state is a major decay channel when in a B-DNA arrangement, whereas its role is less important for A-DNA arrangement and for CG sequence. Moreover, the analysis of our simulations will provide additional insights on the role played by the stacking geometry on the inter-monomer population transfer, showing that the distance between the bases is not the only parameter to be considered.

2 Methods

In this work, we parameterize the following LVC Hamiltonian model considering a set of coupled electronic states in the diabatic basis $|\mathbf{d}\rangle = (|d_1\rangle, |d_2\rangle, \dots, |d_n\rangle)$

$$H = \sum_i \left(K(\mathbf{p}) + V_{ii}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{q}) \right) |d_i\rangle \langle d_i| + \sum_{i,j>i} V_{ij}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{q}) \left(|d_i\rangle \langle d_j| + |d_j\rangle \langle d_i| \right) \quad (1)$$

which depends on the dimensionless normal mode coordinates \mathbf{q} of the ground electronic state S_0 , and their conjugate momenta \mathbf{p} . The kinetic K and potential V terms of the Hamiltonian are defined as

$$K = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{p}^T \boldsymbol{\Omega} \mathbf{p} \quad (2)$$

$$V_{ii}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{q}) = E_{ii}^{\mathbf{d}}(0) + \boldsymbol{\lambda}_{ii}^T \mathbf{q} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}^T \boldsymbol{\Omega} \mathbf{q} \quad (3)$$

$$V_{ij}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{q}) = E_{ij}^{\mathbf{d}}(0) + \boldsymbol{\lambda}_{ij}^T \mathbf{q} \quad (4)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is the diagonal matrix of S_0 vibrational frequencies, reported in Table S27 in the SI, $E_{ii}^{\mathbf{d}}(0)$ is the diabatic vertical energy of state i and $E_{ij}^{\mathbf{d}}(0)$ is a constant electronic coupling between diabatic states i and j , both at the reference geometry (0). The latter term makes the LVC more flexible than in its standard implementation, so to describe the photophysics of multichromophoric systems in terms of local excitations (LEs) and CT states.³⁸ The vectors $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_{ii}$ and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_{ij}$ (with $j \neq i$) have components $\lambda_{ii,\alpha}$, $\lambda_{ij,\alpha}$ (where α labels

the normal mode) which are respectively the gradients of the diabatic potential energy surfaces (PESs) in the reference geometry and the linear coupling parameters. The adiabatic-diabatic transformation is obtained by a recently developed fragment-based diabatization (FrD) thus obtaining a so-called FrD-LVC model.³⁸ According to this approach, we defined diabatic states of the dimer on the basis of reference states that are either the adiabatic states of the fragments/monomers of the dimer (for LEs) or one-electron transitions between orbitals on different fragments (for CT states). In practice, performing the adiabatic-to-diabatic transformation yields a diabatic matrix, which contains the diabatic energies $E_{ii}^d(0)$ on diagonal and inter-state couplings $E_{ij}^d(0)$ on off-diagonal. To obtain the linear couplings $\lambda_{ij,\alpha}$, we displace the geometry of dimer along each dimensionless normal coordinate \mathbf{q}_α by a small amount $\pm\Delta_\alpha$ and we perform a numerical differentiation of the diabatic Hamiltonian.

In our LVC models we included only the effect of intra-base vibrational modes. In practice, nuclear dynamics is described using as a basis the ensemble of the normal coordinates of the two independent monomers. Out-of-plane motions may be anharmonic (and, therefore, not correctly treated by a LVC model) and undergo large-amplitude motion which surely will depend on the environment and the existence of additional nucleobases in the strand. Here, to minimize their impact, inter-molecular modes were frozen, and we imposed C_s symmetry for the two monomers, with the consequence of having four modes with low imaginary frequencies (see Table S27 in the SI). Two modes correspond to the pyramidalization of the NH_2 groups, and two to the methyl rotation. At LVC level these modes in the monomer do not contribute to the dynamics.⁴⁹ Moreover, the methyl groups do not actually exist in the real dinucleotide (and in any case their rotation has a marginal role in our LVC models). Considering that an extensive study of the treatment of low-energy large-amplitude vibrational modes in LVC model falls outside the aim of the present paper, we checked two possible approximations: i) simply turning these imaginary frequencies real and including in the LVC model ii) removing them from the LVC model (which means considering them frozen during the dynamics, thus considering only 89 modes). The results reported in the

main text have been obtained with the first approximation, and are compared in the SI with those obtained with the second ansatz. We shall always highlight which are the predictions more impacted by this choice. This strategy allows to individuate possible cases for which the contribution of these modes is expected to be significant, even if their accurate treatment would require more sophisticated approaches.

3 Computational details

In this work, all the electronic structure calculations have been performed with the Gaussian16 suite of codes.⁵⁰ We used CAM-B3LYP⁵¹ functional in combination with 6-31G(d) basis set, adopting DFT for ground state (GS) and TD-DFT for excited states, to parameterize a FrD-LVC Hamiltonian in order to study the ultrafast photoactivated Quantum Dynamics (QD) of Guanine-Cytosine (GC) and Cytosine-Guanine (CG) stacked bases, arranged according to two possible conformations typical of A-DNA and B-DNA. The effect of the exchange-correlation functional on the computed electronic structure properties was also examined, only for the GC stacked dimer in B-DNA conformation, employing also ω B97XD functional.⁵² In our recently implemented FrD-LVC approach, the reference states to define the diabatic states are defined based on computations on the isolated fragments. A refined version of this approach, named FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC and proposed in ref.⁴⁵ retains the intuitive individual-site basis, but it accounts for the change in LE character and orbital shapes due to the electrostatic effects of the surroundings. This is done by defining reference states from computations for each monomer in the electrostatic field created by the ground state RESP charges of the other ones. In this work, when not stated differently, we use FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC method, but in some cases, for analysis, we compare its results with those of the original FrD-LVC approach.

In the approach adopted in this work, vibrational motion is described in terms of the normal modes of the individual fragments. Concerning the molecular model, as further

explained below, 9-methylguanine (9me-Gua) and 1-methylcytosine (1me-Cyt) are used to represent the guanosine and cytidine in different conformations (see Figure 1).

The initial structures of GC/CG stacked dimers were extracted from the standard fiber B-DNA (twist 36.0° , rise: 3.375 \AA) and A-DNA (twist 32.7° , rise: 2.548 \AA) models according to the 3DNA website.⁵³ We defined eight diabatic states, including the lowest two $\pi\pi^*$ states of cytosine ($C(\pi\pi^*1)$ and $C(\pi\pi^*2)$),^{28,49} the lowest 2 $\pi\pi^*$ states of guanine (L_a and L_b , respectively),⁵⁴ the two lowest $n\pi^*$ of cytosine ($C(n\pi^*1)$ and $C(n\pi^*2)$, mainly corresponding to a $n_N\pi^*$ and an $n_O\pi^*$ excitation, respectively, see Figures S6 and S7 in the SI),^{28,49} the lowest energy $n\pi^*$ state of guanine ($G(n\pi^*)$)⁵⁴ and the lowest energy intra-strand charge transfer (CT) state, i.e. $(G\rightarrow C)CT$. A full projection of the diabatic states on a large-enough set of adiabatic states is necessary in order to properly obtain the parameters of the LVC model, and for this reason we considered a total number of 40 adiabatic states computed at TD-DFT level. The adiabatic-diabatic transformation was computed with a freely distributed code, Overdia, that was developed by some of the authors.⁵⁵

In our procedure,³⁸ optimized (Cs symmetry) 9methyl-guanine and 1methyl-cytosine bases were placed in the standard GC/CG B-DNA and A-DNA arrangement,⁵³ by minimizing the root mean square deviation (RMSD) with the original fiber structures, considering only ring atoms (see SI for more details).

In our FrD-LVC models we included only the effect of intra-base vibrational modes Accordingly, all $N_C=42$ modes of 1me-Cyt and all $N_G=51$ modes of 9me-Gua, a total of $42 + 51=93$ modes, were included in the quantum dynamics simulations. To that aim, a normal-mode analysis was performed for the two individual bases at their C_S minima. Then a set of $2(N_C + N_G)$ molecular structures were generated by displacing the equilibrium structures by an amount $\pm\Delta =0.1$ (dimensionless coordinates) along the N_C modes of 1me-Cyt or the N_G modes of 9me-Gua.

The displaced structures were directly employed to generate the LVC Hamiltonian following the approach described in previous section. The time evolution of the population of

the different diabatic states was then computed by running nonadiabatic quantum dynamics of the vibronic wavepacket with the ML-MCTDH method for 250 fs, as implemented in the Quantics package.⁵⁶ See section S1 of the SI for more details on the ML-MCTDH setup and the graphical representation of the ML trees used for the GC/CG dimer structures studied in this work.

4 Results

Figure 1 sketches the four structures of GC stacked dimers (1me-Cyt and 9me-Gua) investigated in this study. In the SI we report additional figures and tables to better illustrate the different geometrical parameters in the two arrangements. For instance, the distance between the centers of mass (c.o.m.) of the bases for a CG step is smaller in B-DNA than in A-DNA (4.15 Å vs. 4.75 Å), whereas for a GC step we find the opposite trend (3.92 Å for B-DNA and 3.71 Å for A-DNA).

4.1 The CG/GC Stacked Dimers in B-DNA Conformation

4.1.1 Electronic Structure Properties

In Table 1 we report the main features of adiabatic and diabatic states computed for CG and GC B-DNA dimers at the geometries adopted for parameterizing the LVC Hamiltonian, named in the following the Franck Condon (FC) point. For diabatic states we also report their minimum energy computed with the LVC model. The character of the adiabatic states is assigned by inspection of the natural transition orbitals (NTOs) reported in Figures S6 and S7 of the SI. By analysing the energies of the adiabatic states and of the related diabatic states is apparent that the stacking geometry remarkably affects the energies of the LEs on G and C. The LEs on C are indeed more stable in GC (by ≥ 0.1 eV), whereas those on G (though characterized by smaller changes) in CG. However, the most significant effect involves the relative stability of G \rightarrow C(CT), which is much larger in GC, likely due to the

Figure 1: Schematic representation of molecular model of Guanine-Cytosine (GC) and Cytosine-Guanine (CG) stacked dimers in different conformations.

smaller distance of the bases' c.o.m.. In CG dimer, $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ lies indeed at ~ 5.7 eV, and it mixes with the almost degenerate $G(L_b)$ with which it is strongly coupled (0.058 eV, see Table S3 of the SI). Notice in fact the decrease of the oscillator strength of the $G(L_b)$ diabatic state 0.24, which is reduced to 0.13 in the adiabatic state where such character is predominant. This picture is confirmed by the analysis of composition of the adiabatic LVC states (i.e. the eigenstates of the LVC Hamiltonian at the reference ground-state geometry $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}$), which reveals a large mixing between $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ and $G(L_b)$ (see Table S4 of the SI). For GC dimer $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ lies ~ 0.45 lower in energy, at ~ 5.25 eV, very close to $C(\pi\pi^*)$ and especially with $G(L_a)$ with which it is remarkably coupled (-0.043 eV) and is predicted to mix, as confirmed by the analysis of the LVC eigenstates (see Tables S5 and S6 of the SI). Notice in fact the decrease of the oscillator strength of the adiabatic state labeled as $G(L_a)$, which is also coupled with $C(n\pi^*1)$ (see Table 1).

This trend is even more evident when looking at the energy of the minima of the diabatic

Table 1: TD-DFT adiabatic energies (E , in eV), oscillator strengths (f), and their predominant character in terms of NTOs, compared with diabatic state energies at FC point (E^{FC}) and also at their minima (E^{Min}) for the lowest excited states of the CG and GC stacked dimers of B-DNA conformation, predicted with the FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC model Hamiltonian parameterized at CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory.

CG stacked dimer							GC stacked dimer						
Adiabatic				Diabatic			Adiabatic				Diabatic		
State	E	Character	f	E^{FC}	f	E^{Min}	State	E	Character	f	E^{FC}	f	E^{Min}
S ₁	5.120	C($\pi\pi^*1$)	0.097	5.133	0.083	4.751	S ₁	5.001	C($\pi\pi^*1$)	0.075	5.007	0.079	4.502
S ₂	5.292	G(L _a)	0.126	5.302	0.141	4.971	S ₂	5.214	G \rightarrow C(CT)	0.015	5.247	0.000	4.271
S ₃	5.506	C($n\pi^*1$)	0.004	5.511	0.001	4.950	S ₃	5.345	C($n\pi^*1$)	0.047	5.350	0.002	4.633
S ₄	5.661	G \rightarrow C(CT)	0.089	5.699	0.001	4.994	S ₄	5.360	G(L _a)	0.039	5.346	0.130	4.934
S ₅	5.686	G($n\pi^*$)	0.001	5.690	0.001	5.202	S ₅	5.645	G($n\pi^*$)	0.001	5.645	0.000	5.050
S ₆	5.771	G(L _b)	0.127	5.757	0.239	5.384	S ₆	5.744	G(L _b)	0.223	5.755	0.246	5.265
S ₇	6.066	C($n\pi^*2$)	0.001	6.068	0.001	5.379	S ₇	5.894	C($\pi\pi^*2$)	0.152	5.898	0.135	5.283
S ₈	6.103	C($\pi\pi^*2$)	0.161	6.097	0.138	5.609	S ₈	5.982	C($n\pi^*2$)	0.001	5.983	0.001	4.937

states (see Tables S7 and S8 of the SI). The reorganization energy of the diabatic state G \rightarrow C(CT) is ~ 0.7 eV in CG and 1.0 eV in GC. As a consequence, it is by far the most stable diabatic minimum in GC. In CG the most stable diabatic minimum corresponds instead to C($\pi\pi^*1$), whereas G \rightarrow C(CT) is less stable by ~ 0.25 eV, being approximately isoenergetic with G(L_a) and C($n_N\pi^*1$) minima. Interestingly, also C($n_N\pi^*1$) is remarkably stabilized in GC with respect to CG, but even in GC its minimum energy remains 0.4 eV above the G \rightarrow C(CT) minimum.

The picture provided by FrD-LVC model is qualitatively similar to that obtained FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC, with the energy of the large majority of the diabatic states differing by less than 0.1 eV in the two approaches (see Section S2 in the SI), thus showing that the effect of the presence of one base on the definition of the local excitations and orbital shapes on the other base is only moderate.

As far as the linear couplings are concerned (reported in Tables S9 and S10 of the SI), they are systematically much stronger between LEs on the same nucleobase. The largest values are those between G(L_a) and G(L_b) and between C($\pi\pi^*1$) and C($\pi\pi^*2$). Even the mutual coupling of C($n\pi^*1$) and C($n\pi^*2$) and of both these states with C($\pi\pi^*1$) and C($\pi\pi^*2$)

are strong (in line with what already observed for isolated Cytosine in ref.⁴⁹). Interestingly, these couplings are very similar in GC and CG. $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ is more strongly coupled with $G(\text{L}_a)$ and $G(\text{L}_b)$, especially in the GC dimer. The linear couplings between states localized on two different nucleobases are instead much smaller.

4.1.2 Quantum Dynamics of the Electronic Populations

In Figures 2 and 3 we report the results of our quantum dynamical simulations in B-DNA. For CG the amount of charge transfer and excitation energy transfer is quite limited, i.e. most of the decay processes are intra-monomer. In detail, 80% population initially excited on $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ remains on this state, and we simply observe a limited transfer to $C(n\pi^*1)$. 50% of the population of $C(\pi\pi^*2)$ decays to $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ within 100 fs, with a noticeable ultrafast transfer to $C(n\pi^*1)$. Analogously, the population excited on $G(\text{L}_a)$ is not transferred to other states, and most of that excited on $G(\text{L}_b)$ decays to $G(\text{L}_a)$. However, for an initial excitation of $G(\text{L}_b)$ we observe some significant inter-monomer processes. Indeed after 250 fs, 30% of the initial population has been transferred to $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ and 10% to $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$. With this latter exception, the dynamics is similar to that predicted for C and G monomer in the gas phase.^{49,57}

Results are quite similar to those obtained for isolated 9H-Guanine,⁵⁷ for 1me-Cyt,⁴⁹ and the small differences could be due also to the fact that in those papers the larger 6-31+G(d,p) basis set was used.

For GC dimer we predict instead a very different photoactivated dynamics. The amount of $C(\pi\pi^*1) \rightarrow C(n\pi^*1)$ transfer is ~ 0.4 , much larger than for CG. Both for $G(\text{L}_a)$ and $G(\text{L}_b)$ we observe a very large and fast decay to $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$, ~ 0.6 after 50 fs, and ~ 0.8 after 150 fs. The large electronic coupling between the bright states and $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$, (together with the substantial reorganization energy of this latter state), make the dependence of the population transfer on the motion of the tuning vibrational modes to disappear.⁴⁶

These trends can be rationalized on the ground of the relative stability of the different

Figure 2: Population dynamics of the diabatic states of the CG-BDNA structure, starting photoexcitation from $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ (top-left), $C(\pi\pi^*2)$ (bottom-left), $G(L_a)$ (top-right) and $G(L_b)$ (bottom-right) states. FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC Hamiltonian model including 8 diabatic states parameterized at CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level. The dashed lines show the results obtained with the FrD-LVC model.

diabatic states, both in the FC region and in their minima. For GC, $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ is the most stable state coupled to the spectroscopic $G(L_a)$ and $G(L_b)$, whereas $C(n\pi^*)$ is strongly coupled with $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ and have a larger reorganization energy (See Tables S3, S5, S7, S8 in the SI).

Our calculations thus predict that the transfer to $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ is larger for GC than for CG dimer, confirming the trends found when studying GC/CG sequences in duplexes.^{29,31} The main consequence of the presence of the complementary strand concerns the population of $C(n\pi^*1)$, which is negligible in duplexes, due to its destabilization induced by the intramolecular H-bonds.^{29,31} $C(n\pi^*)$ is indeed known to be relatively more stable in the gas

Figure 3: Population dynamics of the diabatic states of the GC-BDNA structure, starting photoexcitation from $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ (top-left), $C(\pi\pi^*2)$ (bottom-left), $G(L_a)$ (top-right) and $G(L_b)$ (bottom-right) states. FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC Hamiltonian model including 8 diabatic states parameterized at CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level.

phase, in the absence of hydrogen bonds.^{49,58}

The trends obtained at the FrD-LVC level are very similar to those described above (see dashed lines in Figure 2 and Figure S8 in the SI).

It is noteworthy that our conclusions are robust with respect to the choice of the functional, as shown by Figure S10 in the SI, where we report the results obtained for GC dimer by using ω B97XD functional. This functional, which provides a description in the FC region of GC dimers close to post-HF wavefunction-based methods,^{39,59} predicts that the CT state is slightly less stable with respect to found by CAM-B3LYP (see also Table S11 in the SI).³⁹ The trends found by CAM-B3LYP functional are confirmed, but the transfer to $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ is smaller (~ 0.6 vs ~ 0.9 after 200 fs).

As shown in section 6 of the SI, this picture does not qualitatively change when the four low-energy vibrational modes discussed above (NH_2 pyramidalizations and CH_3 rotations) are not included in the LVC model. The most significant differences involve the smaller $\text{C}(\pi\pi^*1)\rightarrow\text{C}(n\pi^*1)$ population transfer in GC steps (with a concomitant increase of the $\text{G}\rightarrow\text{C}(\text{CT})$ population).

4.2 The CG/GC Stacked Dimers in A-DNA Conformation

4.2.1 Electronic Structure Properties

The energies of the 8 lowest excited states of CG and GC structures of A-DNA are shown in Table 2. We observe some quite significant differences with respect to the B-DNA results. In A-DNA in fact, the energy of the bright excited states is quite similar in GC and CG steps, i.e. show a less marked dependence on the sequence. $\text{G}\rightarrow\text{C}(\text{CT})$ is still relatively more stable for the GC than for CG but, remarkably, for the latter sequence is significantly less stable than for B-DNA. In the FC region, $\text{G}\rightarrow\text{C}(\text{CT})$ is indeed closer in energy to $\text{G}(\text{L}_b)$ than to $\text{G}(\text{L}_a)$, resulting the fourth lowest energy state (for B-DNA it is the second one). Moreover, though the reorganization energy of $\text{G}\rightarrow\text{C}(\text{CT})$ is the largest one, it is smaller than that found for B-DNA. Consequently, $\text{G}\rightarrow\text{C}(\text{CT})$ is not the most stable minimum. Interestingly, for GC the c.o.m. of the two bases are closer in the A-DNA than in the B-DNA arrangement, indicating that other geometrical parameters, beside the mere c.o.m distance, are relevant for the $\text{G}\rightarrow\text{C}(\text{CT})$ stability (see Table S1 in the SI). One possible factor to be considered is the effect of the stacking geometry on the Coulomb interaction energy (CIE) between the atoms of the different bases, which is important especially for the radical ion pair $\text{G}^+\text{-C}^-$. As a matter of fact, as shown in Table S23 in the SI, it is negative and larger for B-DNA than for A-DNA arrangement.

This result can be explained by the smaller distance existing between atoms bearing substantial formal charges with the same sign in A-DNA stacking arrangement. For example, as depicted in Figure S15, in A-DNA the two nitrogen atoms of the pyrimidine rings of C and

G are aligned face-to-face. As a consequence, the repulsive electrostatic interaction between these atoms is 5.6 kcal/mol larger in GC-ADNA than in GC-BDNA (see Table S23 and Figure S15 in the SI).

Table 2: TD-DFT adiabatic energies (E , in eV), oscillator strengths (f), and their predominant character in terms of NTOs, compared with diabatic state energies at FC point (E^{FC}) and also at their minima (E^{Min}) for the lowest excited states of the CG and GC stacked dimers of A-DNA conformation, predicted with the FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC model Hamiltonian parameterized at CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory.

CG stacked dimer							GC stacked dimer						
Adiabatic				Diabatic			Adiabatic				Diabatic		
State	E	Character	f	E^{FC}	f	E^{Min}	State	E	Character	f	E^{FC}	f	E^{Min}
S ₁	5.152	C($\pi\pi^*1$)	0.079	5.157	0.083	4.635	S ₁	5.000	C($\pi\pi^*1$)	0.027	5.132	0.076	4.578
S ₂	5.277	G(L _a)	0.136	5.281	0.152	4.808	S ₂	5.220	G(L _a)	0.098	5.299	0.125	4.771
S ₃	5.442	C($n\pi^*1$)	0.002	5.450	0.002	4.722	S ₃	5.438	C($n\pi^*1$)	0.003	5.454	0.001	4.696
S ₄	5.696	G($n\pi^*$)	0.001	5.699	0.001	5.146	S ₄	5.605	G($n\pi^*$)	0.005	5.617	0.001	5.027
S ₅	5.745	G(L _b)	0.171	5.771	0.248	5.221	S ₅	5.608	G \rightarrow C(CT)	0.088	5.512	0.005	4.678
S ₆	5.867	G \rightarrow C(CT)	0.024	5.875	0.000	5.123	S ₆	5.743	G(L _b)	0.172	5.782	0.238	5.173
S ₇	5.996	C($\pi\pi^*2$)	0.171	5.992	0.132	5.383	S ₇	5.944	C($\pi\pi^*2$)	0.118	5.972	0.126	5.292
S ₈	6.072	C($n\pi^*2$)	0.001	6.075	0.001	5.257	S ₈	6.042	C($n\pi^*2$)	0.001	6.048	0.001	5.336

4.2.2 Quantum Dynamics of the Electronic Populations

In Figures 4 and 5 we report the diabatic state populations for CG and GC A-DNA structures, following excitations of the lowest energy bright states. For CG the results are similar to that obtained for B-DNA, but for a relatively smaller population of C($\pi\pi^*1$). Indeed, when exciting C($\pi\pi^*1$) or C($\pi\pi^*2$), we observe a larger population transfer to C($n\pi^*1$). Moreover, the amount of excitation transfer from G(L_a) and G(L_b) to C($\pi\pi^*1$) is negligible. Both results can be explained by the smaller relative stability of C($\pi\pi^*1$) in A-DNA with respect to B-DNA (see Tables 1 and 2). For example, C($\pi\pi^*1$) minimum is more stable than the minima of the other intra-monomer excited states by ~ 0.1 eV more in B-DNA than in A-DNA.

GC population dynamics is on the contrary dramatically different in B-DNA and in A-DNA where, independently of the initially excited diabatic state, after 200 fs, the majority of

Figure 4: Population dynamics of the diabatic states of the CG-ADNA structure, starting photoexcitation from $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ (top-left), $C(\pi\pi^*2)$ (bottom-left), $G(L_a)$ (top-right) and $G(L_b)$ (bottom-right) states. FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC Hamiltonian model including 8 diabatic states parameterized at CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level.

the population (≥ 0.5) is on $C(\pi\pi^*1)$. Actually in A-DNA, for initial excitation to $C(\pi\pi^*1)$, $G(L_a)$, and $G(L_b)$, we observe an ultrafast but only transient population of $G \rightarrow C(CT)$, which in less than 50 fs reaches a 0.3~0.4 value. However, at later times $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ population decreases rapidly and it becomes negligible after 200 fs, in line with smaller stability of $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ for A-DNA stacking arrangement, both in the FC region and in their minima.

Apart from the smaller stability of $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ in A-DNA mentioned above, another factor contributing to the different behavior of GC in B-DNA and A-DNA arrangements is related to the electronic coupling between the spectroscopic states and $G \rightarrow C(CT)$. In B-DNA $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ is not significantly coupled with $G \rightarrow C(CT)$, $G(L_a)$, and $G(L_b)$. In A-DNA, where the two bases are closer, the four states are significantly mixed, resulting in the population of the

Figure 5: Population dynamics of the diabatic states of the GC-ADNA structure, starting photoexcitation from $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ (top-left), $C(\pi\pi^*2)$ (bottom-left), $G(L_a)$ (top-right) and $G(L_b)$ (bottom-right) states. FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC Hamiltonian model including 8 diabatic states parameterized at CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level.

diabatic state that is more stable at this geometry (i.e. $C(\pi\pi^*1)$).

It is, however, important to highlight that the picture described above significantly depends on the inclusion of the four low-energy modes. As it is indeed shown in Figure S21 of the SI, for GC-ADNA, the dynamics carried out only with 89 modes predict a significant population transfer (~ 0.5) to $G \rightarrow C(CT)$, after excitation of any of the four bright states. The removal of the four modes with negative frequency has, indeed, a relatively larger impact (~ -0.15 eV) on the reorganization energy of $C(\pi\pi^*1)$, $G(L_a)$ and $C(n\pi^*1)$ than on that of $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ (~ -0.1 eV). These small energy shifts have a remarkable impact on the dynamics, since $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ and $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ minima get extremely close in energy and, at the same time, $G(L_a)$ minimum is further destabilized, leading to a much larger population

transfer to $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$. This result suggests that NH_2 pyramidalization can actually impact the photoexcited dynamics in A-DNA, although more accurate methods are indeed needed to assess such role quantitatively. On the other hand, this process is confirmed to be less favored than for GC B-DNA. For CG steps, finally, 89 modes simulation predicts a smaller $C(\pi\pi^*1) \rightarrow C(n\pi^*1)$ population transfer.

Like for B-DNA, also in A-DNA FrD(MM_{ref})-LVC and FrD-LVC simulations provide a very similar picture of the photoactivated dynamics (see Figures S13 and S14 in the SI).

5 Discussion

In this study we have simulated the photoactivated dynamics of GC and CG stacked nucleobases in B-DNA or A-DNA arrangements, following the population of the four lowest energy bright states, localized on C ($C(\pi\pi^*1)$ and $C(\pi\pi^*2)$) or on G ($G(L_a)$ and $G(L_b)$), i.e. those responsible of the lowest-energy absorption band in GC sequence.

Before discussing the main outcomes of our study, it is important to highlight some of its limitations, in order to put in a better context the relevance of these results for the understanding of the photoactivated dynamics of oligonucleotides.

Our calculations have been performed considering the 'bare nucleobases' in the gas phase, therefore the effect of the solvent is missing, as well as the effect related to the phospho(deoxy)ribose backbone. For what concerns the intra-monomer excitation, the absence of solvent affects mainly $n\pi^*$ transitions (not engaged in intra-molecular H-bonds in single-strand DNA), and, to a lesser extent, $C(\pi\pi^*1)$. The $n\pi^*$ transitions are indeed known to be strongly destabilized (by $0.3 \sim 0.5$ eV)^{3,5} by hydrogen bonds with water molecules, whereas $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ by ~ 0.15 eV.⁵⁸ It is, instead, not easy to predict how solvent would affect the energy of CT states, as $G \rightarrow C$ (CT), at least in the time-window investigated here. As a matter of fact, a full equilibration of solvent degrees of freedom would increase the stability of CT state minima.^{3,60} On the other hand, in our study of Watson-Crick (WC) dimer we

have shown that, on a time-scale < 200 fs, i.e. at the solvent non equilibrium level, an increase of the solvent polarity can lead to a decrease of the stability of G \rightarrow C (CT).⁴⁶

The phospho(deoxy)ribose backbone has instead a more limited effect on the energy of the lowest energy electronic transitions.⁵ Its presence would largely affect the conformational behavior of an oligonucleotide, if thermal fluctuations would have been included in our treatment. This is not an issue here since we considered pairs of nucleobases in different but frozen stacking arrangements.

Our Hamiltonian does not consider the direct ground state recovery from C($\pi\pi^*1$) and G(L_a), which also occur on sub-ps time scale,^{5,54,58} but, it does include potentially-large out-of-plane motion of the ring substituents,⁵ which cannot be reliably treated by a LVC model. As we shall discuss below, we found that these modes can have a deep impact on the simulated dynamics. As a consequence, and also considering the other limitations of LVC models (such as the lack of quadratic couplings and anharmonic effects), the 'time-window' in which the prediction of our simulations is more trustworthy is ~ 100 fs, for which the decay to S₀ of C($\pi\pi^*1$) and G(L_a) is not a dominant process.

Some of the above limitations are, paradoxically, less important when trying to extend the predictions of this paper to the study of duplexes, which is stiffer and less exposed to the solvent than a single strand. However, obviously, we cannot consider any of the effects related to the presence of the complementary chain (e.g. hydrogen bond, proton transfer etc).^{3,5}

Our computations have been performed assuming initial excitations on diabatic states fully localized on individual nucleobases. These states are not eigenstates of the electronic Hamiltonian but they can be assimilated to doorway states that can be excited by laser pulses sufficiently short in time but not so broad in frequency to coherently excite a combination of them. Excitations with sufficiently long pulses might be better simulated populating delocalized states that are eigenstates of the electronic Hamiltonian. Which propagation scheme is more realistic cannot be decided without having in mind a precise experiment.

The assumption we made has the benefit to provide a more immediate interpretation of the dynamics in terms of population transfer between states with a well defined electronic character and, therefore, it provides conclusions that, in our opinion, can be more useful for a qualitative discussion of the main factors into play in the photophysics of these systems.⁴⁵ Moreover, we have checked that, at least when studying an hydrogen bonded GC pair in a WC arrangement, the LVC simulations performed by using as diabatic states the four lowest-energy adiabatic states at the FC position, provided a picture very similar to that obtained with the diabatic states.⁴⁶

As discussed below, however, many of the conclusions of our simulations are not significantly impacted by these limitations. In particular, we show that for B-DNA arrangement the transfer to $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ is an important deactivation channel for the spectroscopic states, especially those localized on G. After 150 fs, $\sim 80\%$ of the population of $G(L_a)$ and $G(L_b)$ has indeed decayed to $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$. This process is instead not important for initial excitations on $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ and $C(\pi\pi^*2)$, which are less coupled with $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$. This trend confirms the results obtained for GC WC dimer^{39,46} and for several GC sequences in duplexes.^{29,31} However, in these latter cases, the transfer to $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ from the spectroscopic states of Cytosine is significantly larger than that found here. However, the small $C(\pi\pi^*1) \rightarrow G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ transfer we find here is mainly an artifact related to the treatment of the four 'negative' low energy modes, as this process is much more relevant when they are kept frozen. Other factors in to play are the increase of the relative stability of $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ in the gas phase that we have discussed above, and the activation of the $C(\pi\pi^*1) \rightarrow C(n\pi^*1)$ channel (see below).

The population transfer to $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ is instead a minor process for CG B-DNA dimer, and even when exciting $G(L_a)$ or $G(L_b)$ it involves less than $\sim 10\%$ of the population. Also in this case, we observe the same trend found in duplex DNA,^{29,31} i.e that population of $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ is larger for GC than for CG sequences, but in duplexes this process is still significant also for CG, involving $\sim 50\%$ of the photoexcited population. As we shall discussed also below, the relative stability of $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ strongly depends on the stacking geometry.

It is not easy to define a single parameter providing a simple description of the stacking geometry. The overlap between the stacked bases is surely an informative value, reminding that many definitions of this parameter are possible.⁶¹ In our study of the duplexes,^{29,31} we have examined a larger set of structures, extracted from MD simulations, increasing the statistical relevance of our conclusions. We indeed found that G→C(CT) was less populated for structures with smaller overlap between the bases (as it happens for CG when compared with GC) and larger c.o.m. distance.²⁹ Please note that in these previous studies,^{29,31} the geometry of the CG bases has been extracted from oligo(GC) duplexes, although adopting a B-DNA like geometry, is different with respect to an 'ideal' B-DNA fiber. It is, thus, interesting to note that the interbase overlap is smaller for CG than for GC sequences, both in 'standard' B-DNA fibers (1.50 Å² vs 2.48 Å², according to 3DNA program)⁶² and in a very large set of experimental DNA and RNA structures.⁶¹

These considerations are sufficient to give account of the smaller CT population in CG steps, which, are significantly 'less stacked' than GC steps. It is instead less straightforward to explain why the population of G→C(CT) is larger for B-DNA than for A-DNA, and this is likely the most biologically relevant outcome of this study, qualitatively confirmed independently of the number of vibrational modes included in the calculation.

Indeed, also for GC A-DNA steps, though some transient population transfer (up to ~40%) to G→C(CT) is predicted within 50 fs from an initial excitation to C($\pi\pi^*$ 1), G(L_a), and G(L_b), we observe a decrease of the G→C(CT) population during the simulation, becoming <10% after 200 fs. At difference of what happens for B-DNA, for A-DNA C($\pi\pi^*$ 1) and not G→C(CT) is the most stable diabatic minimum. It is likely that this result is mainly due to the overestimation of the stability of C($\pi\pi^*$ 1), due to the approximate treatment of the low-energy vibrational modes and to the absence of solvent effects. However, it is noteworthy that G→C(CT) is much more stable in B-DNA than in A-DNA, by 0.4~0.5 eV, both in the FC point and in its minimum (see Table S25 in the SI). The c.o.m. of GC bases are closer in A-DNA than in B-DNA, and indeed the electronic coupling between the

bright excited states and $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$, is larger in the former arrangements. However, the electrostatic interactions between the G^+ cation and C^- anion are stronger in B-DNA arrangement, providing a possible explanation for the larger stability of $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ (see Table S23 in the SI). Interestingly, in this case, the stability of $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ is not directly related to the interbase overlap, which, is larger for GC steps in A-DNA arrangement, according to 3DNA software,⁶² indicating that for closely stacked bases, a more careful analysis of the stacking geometry is necessary.

According to our simulations, another inter-monomer population transfer is relevant for some systems (e.g. GC in A-DNA arrangement), i.e. the excitation transfer from $G(L_a)$ and $G(L_b)$ to $C(\pi\pi^*1)$. The bright excited states on G and C are indeed quite significantly coupled, due to the stacking interactions; as a consequence, for the structures for which $C(\pi\pi^*1)$ is the most stable excited state minimum, we can observe it getting some population from the excited states localized on G. However, this transfer is likely to be an artefact, due to the absence of solvent effects (overstabilizing $C(\pi\pi^*1)$) and of non-radiative decay path from $G(L_a)$ to S_0 , and to the treatment of low-energy vibrational modes. On the other hand, this result highlights that, when studying a closely stacked multi chromophore assembly (MCA), such as DNA or RNA, several excited states can be coupled on the ultra-fast scale, and all the possible deactivation channels have to be mapped on the same foot. For example, here, the extent of population transfer from $G(L_a)$ to $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ does not depend only on the energy and coupling of these two states, but also on their interplay with a third state (e.g. $C(\pi\pi^*1)$), which is effectively coupled to them only for some stacking arrangements (i.e. region of the PES).

For what concerns the other intra-monomer photophysical processes, excitations of the second bright state of G and C lead to a very fast depopulation of the initial state, mainly towards the lowest energy bright state localized on the same nucleobase. Finally, some transfer to $\text{Cyt}(n\pi^*1)$ is possible, due to the absence of solvent/hydrogen bonds which would strongly destabilize this state.

This analysis is confirmed by the outcome of the dynamics on the five GC structures (IS) intermediate between B-DNA and A-DNA, reported and discussed in Section 5 of the SI, enabling to sketch some general rule-of-thumbs for the population of $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ states. Not surprisingly, the dynamics mirror the relative stability/reorganization energy of the diabatic states. $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ states are those exhibiting the largest reorganization energy, confirming the indications of our previous studies.^{11,39,46} The G^+ cation and the C^- anion can reach their optimal geometry ‘independently’ and are stabilized by the onset of favourable electrostatic interactions. In this situation, if the coupling with a given bright state is sufficiently large to allow the ‘transient’ population of the $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$, due to the electronic coupling with the spectroscopic states, it is likely to be ‘irreversible’, i.e. these states deactivate only to ground state. On the other hand, the exact stability of $G \rightarrow C(\text{CT})$ strongly depends on the precise stacking geometry, and, considering that the different minima are quite close in energy, small variations of the arrangements can lead to dramatic differences in the dynamics. The simple evaluation of the electrostatic interactions can provide useful insights on the expected behavior of the different structures (as found when analysing solvent effect),⁴⁶ though for closely stacked MCA this simple analysis should be considered only a preliminary assessment.

The differences between the results obtained including 93 or 89 modes in our LVC calculations highlight the importance of a proper treatment of low-energy vibrational modes, especially, in systems, as NAs, where many minima of similar stability are present. In such cases, relative shifts of 0.05~0.1 eV, connected to the inclusion of some large amplitude motion, can lead to dramatic differences in the dynamical simulations. Such typical LVC limitations are even larger when treating closely stacked systems, for which the possible consequence of any inaccuracy in the description of intra-monomeric degrees of freedom, is magnified by the presence of the other monomer. For example, the error associated to the overestimation of a bond length in one monomer can be larger because it leads to an artificial increase of the steric repulsion with the other monomer. The results of our analysis suggest that excluding these modes from the LVC simulations is likely the safer option. On

the other hand, they allow to point out that especially the NH_2 pyramidalization can have a deep impact on the dynamics especially of A-DNA, although more accurate methods are necessary to properly assess its role. More in general, inclusion of low energy large amplitude modes could be very important for a correct estimate of the reorganization energy of excited state minima characterized by large changes in intermonomeric degrees of freedom, e.g. the stacking distance. A possible approach to these situations involves the use of mixed Quantum/Classical simulations, where low-energy large amplitude modes are treated by classical MD simulations.

It is tempting to hypothesize that these considerations could be valid not only for other DNA sequences, but also for other MCA.³

6 Conclusions

In this paper we report a quantum dynamical study of the photoactivated dynamics of GC and CG stacked dimers in B-DNA or A-DNA arrangements. We assess the population transfers occurring on the ≤ 250 fs time scale among the 8 lowest energy excited states, focussing in particular on the population transfer to the $\text{G} \rightarrow \text{C}$ CT state, a major process in the excited state dynamics in GC-rich oligonucleotides. We show indeed that for GC B-DNA sequence, the bright excited states localized on G, (GL_a) and (GL_b), are strongly coupled with the $\text{G} \rightarrow \text{C}(\text{CT})$, which is substantially populated ($\geq 80\%$) on the ultrafast time-scale. This process is instead less relevant for CG B-DNA and when the bases are in A-DNA arrangement.

These simulations, corroborated by those performed for some GC structures with arrangement intermediate between B-DNA and A-DNA discussed in section 5 of the SI, show that the size of electronic coupling between the bright and the CT state mainly depend on the distance between the bases. On the other hand the stability of $\text{G} \rightarrow \text{C}(\text{CT})$ exhibits a more-complex dependence on the precise stacking geometry and on the sequence, which

strongly modulate the inter-monomer Coulomb interactions. As a consequence, depending on the sequence and on the stacking geometry, the energy of $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ can vary by ~ 0.5 eV in the FC point and even more in its minimum. These differences can prevent the population of $G \rightarrow C(CT)$, even if it is the excited state with the largest re-organization energy.

It is clear that, due to the simplicity of our computational model, any direct translation of our result to the study of polynucleotides is impossible. Some processes (as the large excitation energy transfer to $C(\pi\pi^*1)$) are surely due to the absence of solvent effect. On the other hand, it is interesting to note that the population transfer to $G \rightarrow C(CT)$ is larger for B-DNA (typical of DNA) than for A-DNA (more usual for RNA) stacking geometry. The role of CT states in the oxidative processes in NAs has far from being assessed. On the one hand, it provides a sink for the excitation energy deposited in DNA following UV absorption, that can lead to non-radiative ground state recovery by charge recombination. On the other hand, it could be the door-way for potentially harmful ionization processes.⁶³ Additional experimental and computational studies are thus necessary, the latter tackling the inclusion of the solvent and the treatment of the conformational dynamics of the DNA or RNA chains and its possible impact also on flexible motions on each nucleobase.

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8 Supporting Information

Supporting information available: Section S1: Additional details on the ML-MCTDH setting, with the graphical representation of the ML-MCTDH tree adopted in the QD computations (Figure S1-S4). Section S2. Additional details on the CG/GC stacked dimers in B-DNA and A-DNA conformation, i.e. on their structural features (Figure S5, Table S1-S2), on their electronic states (NTO of B-DNA, Figure S6, S7), on the LVC parameters (B-DNA, Tables S3-S10), and Population dynamics of the diabatic states of the GC-BDNA with the FrD-LVC model (Figure S8). Section S3: Results on the GC stacked dimer in B-DNA conformation studied with the ω B97XD functional, on its electronic properties (NTO, Figure S9), on the LVC parameters (Tables S11-S14) and on the Quantum dynamics of the electronic populations (Figure S10). Section S4: Additional details on the CG/GC stacked dimers in A-DNA conformation, on the electronic states (NTO, Figure S11, S12), on the LVC parameters (B-DNA Tables S15-S22), and on the Population dynamics of the diabatic states with the FrD-LVC model (Figures S13, S14). Section S5. Discussion of the results obtained for the intermediate structures between GC B-DNA and GC A-DNA (Figure S15, Table S23), on their LVC parameters (Tables S24, S25) and on the Population dynamics of the diabatic states (Figures S16-S19). Section S5 Discussion on the impact of flexible modes, reporting the reorganization (Table S26), the vibrational frequencies in S_0 (Table S27) and the Population dynamics of the diabatic states including 89 vibrational modes (Figures S20-S23).

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the acs website.

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